

Detection of Germination Inhibitors in Fruits of *Combretum hartmannianum* Schweinf. Using Biochemical Assays

Mai M. A.Hassan¹, Sayda M. Mohammed¹, Nada B. Hamza²

¹ National tree seed Centre, Forest Research Centre, Agricultural Research Cooperation, Ministry of Agriculture, Khartoum, P.O. Box: 7089, Khartoum, Sudan.

² Commission for Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering, National Centre for Research, Khartoum, P.O. Box 2404 Sudan.

Abstract—*Combretum hartmannianum* is one of the important Sudanese trees which have medicinal uses and high caloric value. This species is at risk of disappearing, as it has very low germination percentage (2% and less), which negatively affect the reforestation efforts of the tree. The low germination percentage might be due to inhibitors produced by the fruit itself. In this study different parts of the fruit were tested to reveal which part of the fruit inhibit the germination and affect the seedlings performance. Two fruit extractions with two concentrations (100fruit/ litre and 200fruit/litre) from the fruit pulp and fruit wings were used to irrigate seeds of *A.mellifera*. The result showed that the high concentration (200 fruit/litre) of both wings and bulb extracts significantly reduced the germination percentage. Although, the root and shoot lengths were not affected, the appearance of the first leaf was delayed. The fruit wings extraction caused abnormal growth of the seedling. Therefore, it can be that the two tested parts of the fruit may contain inhibitors that decrease the germination percentage of this species.

Keywords—*Combretum hartmannianum*, Germination, Inhibitors, fruit extracts.

I. INTRODUCTION

This genetic diversity of forest flora and fauna is a resource of great potential value to the agricultural and pharmaceutical biotechnology industries. However the process of wining valuable genes from millions of species is proving time-consuming and expensive (WRI 2008). Hundreds of tree species worldwide are in imminent danger of being wiped out, according to a report published by WRI (2008).

There was considerable debate about the role of chemical factors in establishing localized communities (Muller et al. 1964). While there were numerous publications of phytotoxic molecules being produced by plants, a phenomenon generally termed allelopathy; it has been known for centuries that walnut trees poison the soil for underlying vegetation (Gries 1942). Some substances that produced naturally by plants were known to inhibit seed germination. These inhibitors don't reduce seed viability or cause any defects in seedling after germination. These inhibitors were found sometimes in the seed coats or fruit pulp or endosperm or embryo. The presence of these inhibitors in plants is common, and some of the natural plant inhibitors that were determined Coumarin, Parascorbic acid, Ferulic acid, ABA, Cyanide – releasing, Ammonia – releasing, Phenolic compounds, Alkaloids,

Organic acids. But ABA is the most widespread natural inhibitor (Zhou, 1998). Their studies show the relation between ABA and embryo stop growing (Sanchez 2003). Some seed extractions inhibit intestinal proteases in snappers' especially alkaline proteases. This inhibition doesn't reduce even after the seeds were treated with acid (Alarocon et al 2001). Germination inhibitors may be located in different parts in the fruit or seed. The most frequent inhibitors are those occurring in fleshy fruit pulp. Even where seeds are sown immediately after harvest, such seeds usually need an extraction and washing to remove inhibitors (Fletcher 1971) In *Prunus Africana* very low germination was achieved when whole fruits were sown, while 75-90 % of the seed germinated after extraction/dipping (Schaefer 1989). Brookman-Amissah (1976) found a chemical dormancy in *Terminalia ivorensis* caused by the presence of Coumerin. Lampo (1990) revealed the presence of 5.88 % of phenols in the pericarp of *Terminalia aviciniodes* fruits. The previous studies in National Tree seed center for the members of the family Combretaceae noticed the poor germination of seeds. Therefore, this study was carried to understand the cause of this problem. There is little knowledge about the nature of the dormancy and the appropriate treatments to break it in the members of the family Combretaceae in general, and in specific the species under study. The evidence of chemicals in fruit coats extract (Mahgoub 2002) could be the main causes of seed dormancy; therefore, there is a need for more investigations and verifications. This work aimed to determine the inhibitory effects of the different parts of *C. hartmannianum* fruit on seed germination and seedlings growth in the early stages. This study is part of the National Tree Seed Centre programme which is designed to solve the tree seeds problems in Sudan; it is a part of other studies that were carried to achieve the goals of the centre.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fruits were collected from Elnour forest at Blue Nile State (in 2006), for extractions the fruit were prepared as follows:

1. Dewinged: The fruits wings were removed, crushed and grinded.
2. De pulped: The fruits pulps were removed, crushed and grinded.

Prepared fruit parts were extracted with methanol in the Aromatic and Medicine plants institute. Every extraction was diluted in one litre of distilled water for two extractions 100 fruits unit/ litre and 200 fruits unit/ litre. Every prepared fruit part was weighted in at 50 grams, this 50 gram was extracted from different numbers of fruits depending on the unit weight. The 50 gram of every unit gave different weighted extracted

* Corresponding Author

substances, so to calculate the effect of 100 and 200 fruits unit (wings, coat and pulp) the next equation was developed:
 Weight of extracted from 100 Or 200 crushed unit =

$$\frac{\text{Weight of extracted substance} \times \text{Weight of 100 or 200 crushed unit}}{50 \text{ gram of each grinded substance (wing, pulp)}}$$

50 gram of each grinded substance (wing, pulp)

Acacia mellifera species was selected because it was fast growing species and it had no inhibitors that may affect the results, so it was selected as a tool of detection of the inhibitors presence or absence. *Acacia mellifera* seeds were sown in Petri dishes in the sand and were irrigated with prepared extractions. 25 seeds in each Petri dish for four replicates to each treatment were done in the experiment. The germination percentage and first leaf emergence for *A. mellifera* were calculated every three days for 15 days. The length of shoot and root were measured. Abnormal seedlings (seedlings with root and without shoot, or seedlings with shoot without root, and discolouration seedlings) were recorded. The CRD (Complete Randomize Design) with four replicates was selected as the experimental design and the statistical analysis was done by JMP package (Programme improved form SAS Package) for analysis of variance, means were compared using Tucky - Kramer.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results show that *Combretum hartmannianum* fruits extractions from fruit pulp and fruit wings in concentration 200fruit /liter significantly reduced the germination percentage of *A. mellifera* seeds (Table 1) (Plates 1, 2, 3, 4, 5). This finding confirmed the results that were obtained by Mahgoub (2002). Who recorded that T. brownii solution reduced the *A.mellifera* germination percentage. This influence was clear from (Plates 1, 3, 4) the sandy soil turned black due to extract deposition, which mean that there were additive components which may affect the germination. These results can be of great value for the medicinal plant scientists and users to try *Combretum hartmannianum* fruit extractions for controlling bacteria and fungi activities and it may be an additional benefit to the medicinal uses of this tree. There is a recent review of lima et al. (2012) who showed that *Combretum hartmannianum* had an anti microbial, anti bacterial, anti inflammatory and anti schistosmal activities.

Combretum hartmannianum fruit extractions have no effects on root length and shoot length of *A. mellifera* seedlings (Table 1). In spite of discoloration of stems that is obvious in Plates (1,4). Which is an indication of negative result on shoot and root growth. That finding indicates that the inhibitory effects of *Combretum hartmannianum* work on failure of seeds germinating rather than reducing of seedling performance (Table 1).

Combretum hartmannianum fruit extractions have significantly delayed the appearance of first leaf of *A. mellifera* seedlings compared with control due to its inhibitory affect (Table 2).

While fruit wings extractions concentration 200fruits/litre seems to be with no difference comparing with control in the first three days, its inhibitory affect appear after 6 days .this

finding indicates that wings extracts have accumulation effects which increases with time (Table 2).

Table 1: Effect of *Combretum hartmannianum* fruits extract of *A. mellifera* seeds germination and seedlings performance

Treatments	Mean of germination %	Mean of shoot length/ cm	Mean of root length/ cm
Control	45.6a	3.1a	2.2a
Seed pulp 200fruit/litre	33.1b	5.5a	1.9a
Seed pulp 100fruit/litre	45.1a	4.9a	1.9a
Seed wing 200fruit/litre	26.9b	4.3a	2.7a
Seed wing 100fruit/litre	43.3a	3.8a	1.9a
	p≤ 0.001	p≤ 0.28	p≤ 0. 28
	SE± 6	SE±0.3	SE±0.3
	CV=32	CV=27	CV=27

Table (2) Effect of *Combretum hartmannianum* fruits extracts on *A. mellefera* seedlings first leaf appearance

Treatments	Mean No of first leaf appearing after 6 days	Mean No of first leaf appearing days9after	Mean No of first leaf appearing after 12days/ No
Control	9.17a	31.7a	39.7a
Seed pulp 200fruit/litre	0b	23.1a	32.7a
Seed pulp 100fruit/litre	0b	16.5a	33.3a
Seed wing 200fruit/litre	4.1a	5.9b	23.1b
Seed wing 100fruit/litre	0b	17.4a	33.7a
	p≤0.018	p≤0.06	p≤0.018
	SE±3	SE±5.5	SE±3
	CV=245	CV=69	CV=245

The results showed that the seedlings of *Acacia mellifera* were significantly affected when were irrigated with *Combretum hartmannianum* extractions (pulp 100, 200 fruit/litre, and wing 200 fruit/litre) (Table 3). The abnormal seedling features such as seedlings with root and failed to emerge cotolydones, or seedlings without roots. This can be evidence that extracts may contain chemical inhibitors that affect mainly the root formation. Such pattern was recorded by Prisco et al. (1978) in wheat when inhibited with salt.

Table 3: Effect of *Combretum hartmannianum* fruit extracts on seedling abnormality *Acacia mellifera*

Treatments	Mean/ No of seedling up normality	Rank
Fruits pulp 100fruit/litre	18.3	a
Fruits pulp 200fruit/litre	18.9	a
Fruits Wings 100fruit/litre	0	b
Fruits Wings 200fruit/litre	14.5	a
Control	2.9	b
$P \leq 0.003$	SE± 3.6	

IV. CONCLUSION

This work concludes that the two parts of the fruit may contain chemicals that may affect the germination and seedlings performance of *Combretum hartmannianum* causing a kind of chemical dormancy. This type of dormancy can be broken by many treatments which leach the chemicals away such as acid treatments, soaking in water. But the main constrain of applying these methods is the perfect time of applying without damaging the embryo and this need further research work to be carried.

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<p>(Plate 1) Effect of <i>C. hartmannianum</i> fruit pulps extraction (100 fruit/litre) on <i>A. mellifera</i> seedlings</p>	<p>(Plate 2) Effect of <i>C. hartmannianum</i> fruit pulps extraction (200 fruit/ litre) on <i>A. mellifera</i> seedlings</p>
<p>(Plate 3) Effect of <i>C. hartmannianum</i> fruit wings extraction(200 frutis/litre) on <i>A. mellifera</i> seedlings</p>	<p>(Plate 4) Effect of <i>C. hartmannianum</i> fruit wings extract (100 frutis/litre) on <i>A. mellifera</i> seedlings</p>

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